

The Theorems Yielded the Coupling Constant Series – Analysis

O Manor

June 7, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing each of the coupling constant series theorems according to its order, a more profound understanding of the 8T can be attained. Such analysis was not presented in the 8T thesis, and thus reader may lack the underlining reasoning of making each of those axioms, as well as the physical meaning of each of those theorems. The purpose of the paper is than to elaborate and expend on the meaning and the reasoning behind those three theorems, which are really the building block of the entire unification between GR and OFT.

Introduction

"Theorem (1) – nature will not allow a prime amount of variation to appear by itself. Define prime to be $(2n+1)$ variations.

1.1) Prime amounts appear in pairs."

Theorem (1) - The physical meaning of that theorem is that bosonic fields cannot be propagated from nowhere. The 8T correlate bosonic propagation to prime net variations of the manifold, and bosons, as we know them, propagate from fermions, which vanish in even number of variations.

Theorem (1.1) – even amount of variations is the result of two prime numbers combined. So to create variation cluster vanishing into matter we need two primes to appear in a pair.

"Theorem (2): Nature will generate force if a **prime net amount of arbitrary variation will appear**. Net variations will appear when combine two amounts of prime variations.

Two does not appear, as it is an even amount of variations, which vanish."

Theorem (2): In continuation of theorem (1), after variation cluster vanished into matter, two distinct elements in threefold combination, a net variation, which is prime can propagate from within it. The feature of the bosonic propagation is their prime number amount of variations, and therefore their expansion across the entire matrix. A boson must propagate from an even amount of variations, which is matter.

Theorem (3): "Each prime pair should have a net variation element N_V proportional to Total Variations value divided by two"

Theorem (3): Each net variation is proportional to the average of the elements in the pair. There could not be net variation $N_V = +(101)$ propagating from (7,11) total variation pair. It does not make sense.

The three theorems in be put in concise and simple manner:

- (1) Bosonic fields cannot propagate from nowhere
- (2) Bosonic Fields propagate from matter clusters
- (3) Bosonic fields are infinite in kind and isomorphic to prime numbers or one.

Theorem (3) was the critical theorem that eventually allowed calculating the value of the fine structure theorem and validating the entire framework.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{0}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{2}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \bigoplus (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \bigoplus (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ...$$

$$(1): (30): (128): (850): (9254) ...$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)